

Corresponding author: Kyoungtae Kim

Email address: kkim@missouristate.edu

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Dear Dr. Paul Whaley,

We wish to submit an original research article entitled "EVALUATING THE EFFECTS OF TIRE POLLUTANTS 6PPD AND 6PPD-Q: AN EXTENSIVE REVIEW COVERING SPECIES SPECIFIC AND INTRACELLULAR TOXIC REPERCUSSIONS" for consideration by the Evidence-Based Toxicology Journal. We confirm that this work is original and has not been published elsewhere, nor is it currently under consideration for publication elsewhere.

In this paper, we report on the toxicity of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q, tire pollutants, at organismal and cellular levels. This is significant because 6PPD and 6PPD-Q are emerging tire pollutants and there are significant knowledge gaps surrounding these toxins. We believe that this manuscript is appropriate for publication by the Evidence-Based Toxicology Journal because it focuses on a systematic review of ecotoxicology, aquatic toxicology, and the toxicological effects of the anthropogenic tire pollutants, 6PPD and 6PPD-Q.

In this review we aimed to connect the common themes of toxicity observed within organism and cellular models. This is a novel review because a majority of previously published works focus solely on organismal effects of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q. We focused on the mortality and inflammatory effects of 6PPD and 6PPD-Q within aquatic, terrestrial and *in vitro* models. Our manuscript would be a great addition to Evidence-Based Toxicology Journal, because 6PPD and 6PPD-Q are not currently EPA regulated, and we hope our work will help drive future research trends leading to regulation policy formation. For these reasons we believe the readership of Evidence-Based Toxicology will be interested in learning the current research surrounding 6PPD and 6PPD-Q and possible ways to remedy the knowledge gaps. To help further edit our manuscript we would like Brian Alper, Guyan Bowatte, Geoff Frampton, Thomas Hartung, and Haneen Khreis, to review our work.

We have no conflicts of interest to disclose.

Please address all correspondence concerning this manuscript to Dr. Kyoungtae Kim, kkim@missouristate.edu.

Thank you for your consideration of this manuscript.

Sincerely,

Kyoungtae Kim (Professor in Biology at Missouri State University).